

European Venom Network Virtual Networking strategy

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In the second grant Period, the **European Venom Network** counted with 105 registered members, divided in 5 Working Groups (WGs) and 4 Horizontal Committees (HCs). The number of total participants diminished about 40% from the first Grant Period (170 members). This was most likely due to the enforcement of a new COST Association procedure which required a formal application through the eCOST system to request joining a COST Action WG and officially become an Action member. However, we expect a continued growing of the network, in particular with the addition of International Partner Countries. Moreover, a turnover in the key positions (WG and committees' leaders and co-leaders) is expected. This document is an updated version of the previous Virtual Networking Strategy and is intended to function as a guide to support virtual activities during the entire lifecycle of the European Venom Network Action. The main objectives are:

- To facilitate fast and effective communication and collaboration among all the participants, by promoting and implementing the use of managerial and networking tools.
- To facilitate their active participation through the entire lifetime of the Action.
- To propose a new set of policies and networking tools in order to comply with the regulations of the European Commission.
- To assure an effective heritage beyond the Action lifecycle.

The updated version of the strategy has been presented and accepted by the Management Committee on 31/10/2022 and it includes all the suggestions and improvements that were received. However, this is a living document, and shall be revised and updated yearly.

1. Personal data gathering

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) dictates specific requirements with which businesses must comply to protect the personal data privacy of EU citizens. The regulation also includes the monitoring of data that is exported outside the EU. GDPR is important because it improves the protection of European data subjects' rights and clarifies what companies that process personal data must do to safeguard these rights. All companies and organisations dealing with data from EU citizens must implement the regulations to ensure a secure environment for their customers. Individual consent is at the basis of data storage and transfer. At the same time, individuals have the right to know where the data is being stored and how it is being processed. They also have the right to request corrections or deletion of the stored personal information.

Following these principles, the collection of emails and personal information from any person interested in the Action must comply with this regulation. To comply with GDPR, a **privacy policy**¹ was developed and published on the Action website. The Google form previously used to collect information of Action members was not needed anymore because of the new procedure to register as Action member through eCOST and it was consequently eliminated.

The privacy policy will be revised yearly in order to include any potential change in the EU legislation or to include processes that were not forecasted at the beginning.

2. WGs and HCs communication

The main communication tool for networks of researchers is usually email. This is not amenable for long-term projects such as COST Actions. Documents, decisions and deliverables have to be readily available at any time along the 4 years of the Action lifetime. In addition, deliverables and milestones monitoring and tracking need to be clearly defined and shared among the Action participants. To allow a smooth transmission of information, three main virtual channels were set up:

- A Slack channel including all the Action participants and stakeholders (e.g. amateurs, researchers from other fields, private sector). Slack is a software dedicated to fast communication among projects participants. Thanks to the mobile

¹ <https://euven-network.eu/privacy-policy/>

app, it can be installed on Android/iOS, and function as a reliable tool for fast chat-like communication.

- A dedicated project table in Trello. Trello is an application to track the time and the development stage of a project. WGs leaders and co-leaders have been invited to subscribe and follow the development of their WG deliverables/milestones. In addition, invited subscribers can edit and contribute in a collaborative manner to each project task on Trello, by adding/deleting tasks and documents.
- Document sharing and storage will be done through Dropbox. Dropbox is a cloud-based storage infrastructure that is compliant with GDPR and EU regulation of data security and storage. For each WG and HC, a shared Dropbox folder will be set-up and maintained. The purpose is to always store the last version of the documents related to the corresponding WG/HC. A dedicated folder for Core Team meetings will also be maintained, in which minutes, decisions and notifications will always be available to the members for consultation.

My role as Virtual Networking Manager (VNM) is to set up and keep the three channels updated with all the necessary documentation, moderate channels, and assure that all the participants are informed about the Action activities, Grants, events and opportunities.

It turned out that Trello was not effectively used by the WG leaders, and so it was dismissed. The Slack channel and the Dropbox folder were maintained.

Email communication will be also maintained, but only as a way of communication for the Core Team, and not to the whole community.

In the effort of keeping a link with members who registered during GP1 using the Google form but did not officially register through the eCOST portal in GP2, the traditional email communication was replaced by a Mailchimp newsletter. The email database of GP1 Action participants was merged with the new membership requests. As VNM, I am maintaining a regular newsletter to announce grants, events and Core Team decisions, and to inform all the participants of the Action of our progress in different areas. The landing page to register to the EUVEN newsletter is now linked on the website.

To assure the open access to all the materials produced by the Action, an EU-compliant storing strategy is outlined below (chapter 4).

3. STSM Knowledge Transfer

Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) are short transnational visits between COST member states included in the Action. The aim is not only to foster individual mobility of Action members, but also to promote the sharing of all the research infrastructure and methods represented in the Action. STSMs are individual grants. The nature of the grant may result in an individual experience as sole prerogative. To promote the transfer of knowledge from the grantees to the entire Action, an additional requirement to the grantee is introduced here: the “Transfer of Knowledge Report” (TKR). An activity report is already a mandatory requirement for every successful STSM grantee. This is, however, an internal scientific report that confirms that the STSM objectives have been successfully achieved and it is not shared among the Action members. The newly implemented TKR represents the description of particular knowledge created as part of the STSM (for instance a novel technique, a protocol, a script, etc.). The TKR will be published by the VNM on a specific section of the website along with the STSM grantee name and contact. In this way, the knowledge of a single STSM can be translated into a tangible output from which the whole Action can benefit. Other people may eventually use the methods, contact the reference person, and upload (by requesting to do so to the VNM) a revised version of the method if needed. The VNM will be in charge of promoting the creation and maintenance of such material, ensure its quality, and facilitate the updates.

4. Storage of Action material

Open access is the practice of providing online access to information that is free of charge to the user and is reusable. It is now widely recognised that making research results more accessible to all contributes to better and more efficient science, and to innovation in the public and private sectors. The COST Association supports open access specifically in its funding programmes. Consequently, COST Actions should, whenever possible, freely share knowledge and results for the benefit of the research community and society at large.

As part of the online dissemination strategy of EUVEN results and outputs, all the documentation produced by the Action is deposited in ZENODO². ZENODO is a recognized online multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN and guarantees the full compliance with the data management requirements of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. When the number of uploaded documents grows, the VNM

² <https://zenodo.org>

will evaluate the opportunity to create a ZENODO “community”, which is a nested repository within ZENODO that collects all the results coming from the EUVEN Action. All the documents have to include metadata, with at least the following information: *i)* the full title of the COST Action “European Venom Network”, *ii)* the COST Action number “CA19144”; and *iii)* the acronym “EUVEN”.

5. Events calendar

During the first GP, only a few events took place and where mainly in a virtual setting, such as conferences and meetings. Occasionally, Action members have notified some of those events to the Action Chair and the GH manager who took care of disseminating this information by sending an email to the EUVEN mailing list. The Communications team, when informed, was in charge of posting events on social media. Most of the times, the event announcement was directly made through the official social networks of the Action, for instance by tagging EUVEN to Twitter posts. The fragmentary nature of these information, plus the non-uniform way to collect it, may hamper knowledge exchange across the network.

With the purpose of collecting and disseminating information on events that might be interesting for Action members, a dedicated form was created during GP1. The form is meant to collect a minimal set of information for the event to be advertised through the EUVEN network. Unfortunately, the tool was not utilized by the members, and never really implemented in an effective way. To overcome this issue, the VNM will check bimonthly during the Core Team meetings for upcoming events that may be of interest for Action participants. The information will be uploaded on the dedicated calendar on the EUVEN website, disseminated via the newsletter, and transmitted to the Communications team for a timely and coordinated diffusion of the event.

6. Infographics to support virtual events

At the end of GP1, a number of virtual events were planned to be held during the GP2 (webinars, training school, seminars). To support such events with adequate dissemination materials, a Canva account was created. Canva is an online graphic design tool that allows users with minimal know-how in graphic design to create professional digital materials. As VNM, I participated in short free courses on graphic

design and provided support with the creation of digital materials to all virtual events of GP2 (agendas, infographics, dissemination flyers, twitter ads, participation certificates and others). The new tool has proven to be very time- and cost-effective, as it does not rely on external companies. The tool will be maintained for the next years of Action lifetime.